

Research Software focus area Maturity Model: Methodology

Deekshitha¹, Rena Bakhshi², Jason Maassen³, Carlos Martinez Ortiz⁴
Rob van Nieuwpoort⁵, Antti Knutas⁶, and Slinger Jansen⁷

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This document includes a detailed description of the methods used in the Research Software Project Management focus area maturity model (RSMM) [See Figure 1 for an overview of the model].

1 Systematic Literature Review (SLR)

We used four databases, **ACM Digital Library**, **Google Scholar**, **Scopus**, and **IEEE Xplore**, to collect articles related to our topic. The steps of this process are outlined below:

- a) **Collecting all initial literature.** The initial literature collection was obtained through a search of selected databases. This initial search included querying the complete text, abstract, title, and keyword sections using the search query: "Research software" AND ("management" OR "project management" OR "practice" OR "capability" OR "lifecycle"). This search query was developed following a preliminary exploration of the topic, which included discussions among the authors, and initial review of the literature. The keyword "project management" was included based on the observation that research software is frequently developed within structured projects that employ management frameworks similar to those used in industrial software development. The broader term "management" was also included to capture literature that addresses organizational, operational, and strategic aspects of research software development. The terms "practice" and "capability" were included to capture literature addressing methodologies, competencies, and best practices specific to managing research-oriented software. Lastly, the keywords "lifecycle" was included based on the observation that these concepts are related to the management of research software, particularly in relation to its development, maintenance, and long-term sustainability.

The search across the selected databases resulted in a total of 41,717 articles. Table 1 presents a detailed overview of the results.

- b) **Applying inclusion criteria.** The body of literature generated in the previous step was examined for the presence of the keywords of the search query in the title, abstract, and keyword sections. Additionally, the inclusion criteria were applied to refine the selection further. This method resulted in a total of 163 articles. The following inclusion criteria were applied to refine the literature: (i) written in English; (ii) has a document body consisting of more than one page. (iii) is a book, research paper, thesis or whitepaper; (iv) is open access; (v) is published in or after 2014 (we cover the last decade of data).
- c) **Removing duplicates.** The reference lists for each selected database containing literature that passed the inclusion criteria applied in the previous step were cross-referenced with one another. After cross-referencing, any duplicates were removed, resulting in a total of 124 articles.
- d) **Applying exclusion criteria.** Next, all books, research papers, thesis, and white papers in the remaining collection were examined for the presence of practices or capabilities. Only the literature containing any of these elements was selected. As a result, practices and capabilities were identified from 50 articles. We refer an interested reader to an example in Table 7 showing practices associated with the first focus area and their reference literature. References for all other practices and capabilities are provided in the published dataset (Deekshitha et al., 2025).

Maturity levels	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	Software Project Management									
1										
Requirements		File issues in an issue tracker	Act on feedback				Manage requirements explicitly	Perform release management		Communicate roadmap
Code quality and security	Provide a coding standard	Conduct code reviews	Implement continuous integration	Provide executable tests	Use crash reporting	Conduct security reviews	Measure project stability continuously	Define code coverage targets	Execute tests in a public workflow	Follow an industry standard for security
Communication and collaboration			Store project in public repository with version control				Use public communication platform	Provide news letter		Provide community website
	Research Software Management									
2										
Impact measurement		Define a clear audience for the project	Perform infrequent impact measurement				Evaluate whether the audience's goals are met		Perform continuous impact measurement	Explore new audiences regularly
Sustainability		Acquire temporary funding		Write software management plan			Obtain support from a national research software center	Acquire viable pathways for project sustainability	Secure continuous funding	Define end-of-life policy
Visibility	Make code citable		Enable indexing of project meta-data	Promote the project continuously	Publish in a research software directory	Acquire research software center acknowledgement	Enable indexing of the project's source code			Garner industrial partner adoption
Usage costs & Ethics			Analyze privacy usage impact		Analyze ethical consequences of project use	Document the cost of running the application	Consider total energy consumption			
	Community Engagement									
3										
Partnerships				Acknowledge partners and funding agencies on website			Develop advanced partnership model			
Community			Impose community norms	Onboard researchers as part of the community	Develop code of conduct	Appoint support team	Organize community events		Provide front page chat support	Focus on diversity and inclusion
Developers		Make developer names and roles publicly available				Document how to join the team		Set maximum response time for developer training and pull requests	Provide access to developer training and skill development	
Licensing	Select a license		Get institutional support for license choice					Evaluate license policy regularly		
	Software Adoptability									
4										
Ease of use		Provide a statement of purpose	Provide a simple how to use guide			Provide online tutorials				
Documentation		Provide a read me file with project explanation	Provide a how-to guide	Provide a common example usage		Provide a documentation as repository/documentation wiki		Provide API documentation		
Technology		Use common non-exotic or established technology		Facilitate integration into scientific workflow					Evaluate technology relevance regularly	
Reproducibility		Provide instructions on how to put into research workflow		Provide instructions on how to make part of a replication package	Make part of standardized workflows		Make part of a replication package			
Education				Develop generic educational materials					Organize training events in person	Make project part of an educational program
Deployability					Provide with standard deployment tools			Enable deployment on a wide range of technology	Provide coordination mechanisms for workflow distribution over different machines	Generate SBOM

Figure 1: RSM v1.0: The updated version of RSM. It includes 4 focus areas, 17 capabilities, and 79 practices. These practices are placed between maturity levels 1-10.

	ACM Digital Library	Google Scholar	Scopus	IEEE Xplore	Total
Collecting all initial literature	1,411	24,300	397	15,609	41,717
Applying inclusion criteria	7	80	59	17	163

Table 1: The number of articles collected and remained after applying the inclusion criteria, per academic database.

The references for the practices in the first focus area are provided in Table 7. Some sources cover multiple practices; a few include corresponding capabilities’ names within the same articles. Some practices are found in more than one of the articles, but we have included only a few in Table 7.

Table 2: Practices and its references

Practices name	Found in (references)
Requirements are managed explicitly	(Carver et al., 2022; Eisty and Carver, 2022a; Eisty et al., 2018)
Authors act on feedback	(Ye et al., 2021)
Roadmap is communicated	(Ye et al., 2021; Barker et al., 2022)
Code reviews are executed	(Ye et al., 2021; Eisty and Carver, 2022a; Vedder et al., 2021)
Security reviews are conducted	(Ryan et al., 2023; Ye et al., 2021)
There are executable tests	(Katz et al., 2019; Eisty and Carver, 2022a; Vedder et al., 2021)
Tests are executed in a public workflow	(Eisty and Carver, 2022b; Ye et al., 2021)
Uses common methods for security evaluation	(Ryan et al., 2023; Ye et al., 2021)
Project stability is measured continuously	(Eisty and Carver, 2022b)
Crash reporting is used	(Quach, 2022)
A public repository system is used	(Quach, 2022; Ye et al., 2021)
Has a watering hole for community members	(Butler et al., 2021; Ye et al., 2021)
An infrastructure is available for posting issues	(Ye et al., 2021)
Issues are actively worked on	(Ye et al., 2021; Quach, 2022)
There is a support team in place	(Ye et al., 2021)

Table 3: The table provides information on the interviewees, including their current roles within their organizations, years of experience in developing or managing research software projects, and the interview mode. Notably, only one interview was conducted in person.

Interviewee	Experience	Interview mode
Professor	10+ years	Online
Professor and Research Scientist	10+ years	Online
RSE	10+ years	Online
Co-leader and Lead RSE	10+ years	Online
Research Scientist	4 years	Online
Deputy Head of Division Computing	10+ years	Online
Research Group Leader	10+ years	Online
Assistant Professor	10+ years	Online
RSE	7 years	Online
RSE	10+ years	Online
Programme Manager	10+ years	Online
Section Head	10+ years	Offline

2 Expert Interviews

We contacted Dutch and German RSE groups, providing an overview of the project and inviting voluntary participation. We received 15 positive responses and then shared the interview protocol. Ultimately, 12 confirmed participants met our selection criteria, which required experience managing research software projects to ensure valuable insights from their work. Table 3 details the selected experts and the interview modes used. We scheduled online team meetings based on the participants’ availability. The interviews lasted between a minimum of 45 minutes and a maximum of 1 hour and 36 minutes.

We utilized Miro, an online collaborative workspace at the experts’ interview stage, to facilitate the card-sorting task. Figure 2 shows a screenshot of the small part of the maturity model template shared with the experts. We started the first expert interview with this template. During the interview, experts categorize the practices into capability groups, considering their maturity level and the maturity of neighbouring practices. After each interview, we updated the template with the practices suggested by the previous expert. This way, the template was modified after each interview and sent to the next interviewee.

Figure 3 compares the focus area maturity model templates provided by the three experts. It illustrates the arrangement of practices within the first capability, **Requirements**, based on their inputs. The maturity levels were determined by taking the mode of the rankings assigned by the experts. We also considered dependencies between different practices within a capability and other capabilities in the same focus area and the various focus areas for the final placement of practices. For example, out of 12 experts, four recommended positioning the *Provide executable tests* practice at level 4. Then, we assigned this practice to maturity level 4, considering its dependencies with another practice, *Execute tests in a public workflow*. It is because the practice, *Provide executable tests* must be implemented or executed before the *Execute tests in a public workflow*. Additionally, we revised the practice names to follow the ‘Verb Object (Qualifier)’ pattern. We also made minor adjustments to the names of the focus areas and capabilities. These revisions resulted in the development of RSMM v1.0.

Figure 2: A screenshot of the RSMM v0.1a template: The practices of RSMM v0.1 are displayed in green boxes, and the capabilities are in yellow boxes. Separate components represent each focus area.

Model	Focus Areas	Capabilities	Practices	Modified	Replaced	Merged	Maturity Levels
RSMM v0.1	4	18	61	-	-	-	7
RSMM v1.0	4	17	79	5	3	1	10

Table 4: Statistical comparison between two RSMM versions

Table 4 provides details on the changes made in RSMM v1.0 compared to RSMM v0.1. During the transition from v0.1 to v1.0, 18 new practices were added during expert interviews. Additionally, the **Issue management** capability has been merged with **Requirements** and **Community**. Two practices of the **Issue management** capability have been combined and moved to the **Requirements** capability. The **Code quality** capability has been updated and renamed to **Code quality and Security**. Three of the practices from the other capabilities also moved to other capabilities as per the suggestions from the interview participants. However, we needed more

Figure 3: Maturity model template by experts: The screenshot depicts three experts' ranking of practices within the **Requirements** capability, illustrating their placements in the RSMM v0.1a expert's dashboard.

data for practices introduced during the final interviews to determine their maturity levels. As a pragmatic solution, we placed these practices in RSMM v1.0 according to the maturity levels suggested in the most recent interviews; because of this, we sent RSMM v1.0 to the interviewees for confirmation. So, experts reviewed the new additions and provided any final feedback or suggestions for further refinement of RSMM v1.0. One of the comments we received was “*Yes, I will use input from this model in my future work*”, which we perceive as encouraging. We used ATLAS.ti (Smit and Scherman, 2021) to conduct the thematic analysis of the expert feedback, and the evaluation results are presented in following section.

3 Evaluation

Question 1 Do you think this model fully reflects the maturity of research software projects that develop research software, or are there aspects missing?

The question was asked to the interview participants to assess the completeness of RSMM in evaluating the maturity of research software projects. The responses are categorised into themes, and the results are provided below:

- **Concerning model coverage:** Six out of 12 experts agreed that it covers most of the aspects of maturity, with some describing it as comprehensive and inclusive of various dimensions. For instance, one participant stated, *“...it is very complete as I see it, at least to me it appears in terms of dimensions, it seems quite complete...”*. Another noted its broad coverage of practices and multiple aspects, including use and quality. However, one interviewee highlighted overlap with other maturity models, remarking, *“In some sense, yes. It’s one of many other maturity models that checks this”*. Despite these observations, one of the experts acknowledges that RSMM addresses various “ages” of the problem in defining what makes research software mature and highlights the difficulty in defining maturity comprehensively. *“Yeah, I think so. I think that you are considering a lot of different ages of the problem because it’s [it was] never easy to define maturity....”*
- **Applicability of maturity model criteria:** Two experts highlighted that not all aspects of a maturity model apply to all the projects, as some criteria may be project-specific and depend on the context of the software. Because the higher maturity levels of practices may not apply to every project. However, the main aim of RSMM is to help research software-producing organisations to help and improve their research software project management. However, the main aim of RSMM is to help research software-producing organisations improve their project management practices. RSMM is a structured framework that offers guidance on evaluating and improving the maturity of various aspects of research software projects, such as software development, community engagement, and sustainability. While the model may not apply in the same way to every project, it acts as a tool to help organisations identify areas for improvement, prioritise practices based on their unique needs, and finally, improve the management, visibility, and impact of their research software projects.
- **Involvement of software developers in judging maturity:** One of the suggestions we received is to focus on identifying important practices in judging maturity. It was noted as follows: *“I think if you would have sort of a little survey for both the user and the developers that would ask them what is important first and then to evaluate the extent to which it’s obtained, I would say that you would get a pretty good image”*. We consider this a valuable suggestion, as the design of RSMM already incorporates case studies with developers of research software projects to explore the maturity of their projects. The expert interviews also started by asking experts about the important factors for determining maturity.

In total, six experts suggested that RSMM includes a wide range of practices relevant to research software project management, addressing factors that define the maturity of research software projects and appears comprehensive. However, two experts disagree, noting that RSMM may not apply to all projects, and four experts expressed mixed opinions, acknowledging that RSMM seems complete and incorporates various aspects but emphasised

the need for a stronger statement on maturity and the importance of software developers evaluating the practices.

Question 2: Do you think RSMM helps organisations improve their research software production practices? This question assesses the practical impact of RSMM on organisations. The identified themes are provided below:

- **Practical application and Effectiveness:** From the expert’s perspective, RSMM is a valuable tool for organisations, helping them structure and improve their research software project management capabilities. Many participants mentioned that this study suggests a good model with several best practices to help organisations or principal investigators know how they are doing in the community, research software management, and other areas. Additionally, it helps to determine the next steps needed to improve their project capabilities.
- **Guidance for developers and institutions:** The experts highlighted that RSMM can be used as a guide, which assists RSEs and organisations in improving their research software project management and decision-making processes. It recommends best practices and sets goals across different categories or capabilities, helping RSEs and organisations improve their practices.
- **Limitations of RSMM:** The same concern about the RSMM applicability arises once again. Three responses highlighted that not all practices are suitable for every project. It is necessary to evaluate the relevance of RSMM based on individual projects’ specific objectives or goals.

“...I think it can give some pointers, some hints on what people could follow on and what people could focus on. But it yeah, to decide whether this is relevant for a specific project or not would still be up to the yeah people....”

However, RSMM is designed to allow users to exclude specific capabilities or focus areas they do not aim to achieve maturity while evaluating research software project management.

- **Evaluating the progress or maturity over time:** An expert highlighted that RSMM would be especially valuable if it could monitor changes over time, stated that *‘...can assess the maturity level of my software at different points in time; then I will say yes, it will help.’* RSMM can be used to know where to make changes and improve the process over time.
- **Need for the documentation:** Due to many practices, some experts expressed confusion regarding the names of specific practices, and few of the practices are unfamiliar. One expert emphasised the need for documentation to clarify the meaning of each practice, which would help users of RSMM better understand and apply RSMM. During the expert interviews, they asked questions to clarify specific practices they found challenging to understand.

We received four positive, four negative, and an equal number of neutral responses for the above question.

Question 3: How easily can organisations adapt RSMM to improve their practices?

From this question, we want to test the adaptability of RSMM.

- **Ease of use:** Six fully confident responses were received about the ease of use of RSMM. Since it aligns with the practices they regularly implement.
- **Complexity:** Some experts pointed out that specific terms used in the practices of RSMM may not be easily understood by all users. For instance, "Watering Holes for Community Members" was noted as unclear, and the same for "Generate SBOM". In response to the expert's suggestion, these terms have been revised to ensure clarity and accessibility for a broader audience. Additionally, one expert remarked, "*It says performs continuous impact measurement, but it does not specify how this impact would be measured*". This feedback highlighted the lack of clarity in the practice, *Performs continuous impact measurement*. The expert expressed the need for more detailed information about such practices. We have developed a comprehensive dataset that provides detailed descriptions of all the practices within RSMM to improve the understanding and usability of RSMM.
- **Automatic tool for maturity assessment:** Two experts suggested automating RSMM so that every stakeholder of RSMM can easily use it.

"...maybe building an automatic tool for this model, evaluating the resources of the projects, what is missing in that project or evaluating their quality with this model... I think in particular an automatic tool could be very helpful to, yeah, give guidance on on what is missing..."

We are also considering the development of an automated tool for RSMM, which is part of the future work.

Six experts mentioned that RSMM is easy to adopt. In comparison, four experts expressed concerns, noting that RSMM includes many practices, some of which are unclear or difficult to implement. Additionally, two experts emphasised the need for automated tools to facilitate the evaluation process and the importance of documenting all practices for better clarity and accessibility.

In addition to the evaluation questions, we asked experts about the intended users of RSMM to understand who might benefit from RSMM based on their experience with the tool. The responses aligned primarily with our expectations, identifying the primary users as researchers, RSEs, and funders. Project managers, academic institutions, and research organisations were also mentioned as users. The responses are as follows:

"Researchers, academics who spend a significant amount of their time developing and managing research software."

"Researchers working with research software. Funders will find these metrics useful. Industries and companies working with research might also benefit."

Table 5: Evaluation table: Results from expert interviews

Questions	Themes	Example excerpt(s)
Do you think this model will accurately reflect the maturity of research projects that develop research software?	Concerning model coverage and accuracy	<i>"...you [RSMM] cover a broader range of, yeah, many practices,... And also different aspects of the software, not only the use and quality..."</i>
	Applicability of maturity model criteria	<i>"I think it touches on a lot of aspects that go into the maturity of projects. Not all the aspects are necessarily applicable to each project..."</i>
	Involvement of software developers in judging maturity	<i>"...I think if you would have sort of a little survey for both the user and the developers that would ask them what is important first and then to evaluate the extent to which it's obtained, I would say that you would get a pretty good image."</i>
Do you think this model helps organisations improve their research software production practices?	Practical application and Usability	<i>"I do think it can help. Having such a model can make it explicit to for an organisation to know what they should be doing..."</i>
	Guidance for developers and institutions	<i>"yes, I think the model [RSMM] can help, but more a software guideline for the institution. The guideline can refer to such a maturity model and such software policy can establish A framework for the developers and help them to guide them in their daily work. And yes, and can provide some recommendations about best practices and about the goal which can be achieved in different categories."</i>
	Limitations of RSMM	<i>"...I think it can give some pointers, some hints on what people could follow on and what people could focus on. But it yeah, to decide whether this is relevant for a specific project or not would still be up to the yeah people..."</i>
	Evaluating the progress or maturity over time	<i>"... can assess the maturity level of my software on different time lapses, then I will say yes, it will help."</i>

Question	Themes	Example excerpt(s)
	Need for the documentation	<i>“...if you have that as a road map, right, then you can feel towards better practices, right? The organisation can do more than individual researchers might not want to go through as well...”</i>
How easily can organisations adapt this model to improve their practices?	Ease of use	<i>“easy. For applications, its checklists are much easier...”</i>
	Complexity	<i>“...I find that word a bit odd in this context, so the terminology should not scare away people....”</i>
	Automatic tool for maturity assessment	<i>“...maybe building an automatic tool for this model, evaluating the resources of the projects, what is missing in that project or evaluating their quality with this model. I think in particular an automatic tool could be very helpful to, yeah, give guidance on on what is missing...”</i>

Table 5 includes more example excerpts for each theme. The following subsection discusses the survey conducted with the 8 participants.

3.1 Expert confirmation

During the confirmation step, a small survey is shared with the interview participants when RSMM v1.0 is sent to them for confirmation. The survey questions are listed below, and the themes are not extracted separately from the responses as they include a small amount of data.

Question 1 (Effectiveness): Does RSMM accurately represent our discussions?

The question assesses whether the discussion points raised during the interviews are consistent with the model we developed. We received five positive responses from our experts. Three acknowledged some deviations in the final model, RSMM v1.0, due to the aggregation of different experts’ perspectives, and the outcome reflects the discussions. One of the participants responded as follows: *“According to my notes, the order of the indicators for the respective levels does not correspond exactly to how I had lined it up on the Miro Board. But that is not to be expected when the input from different interviews is combined...”*. We provided RSMM v0.1 model during the interview without the maturity levels. This model had been developed using the Miro dashboard, where practices were arranged according to their corresponding capabilities. The interviewee’s comment is about the arrangement on the Miro Board.

Question 2 (Usefulness): Do you find RSMM useful?

We received seven positive responses to this question, with participants agreeing that RSMM is valuable. They indicated that the model can effectively guide users and inspire improvements in

the capabilities of the research software management. One of the experts emphasised the value of RSMM in assessing adherence to maturity levels and inspiring improvements in capabilities: “Yes, insofar as it can be good to see what parts of maturity in the software, we are and aren’t adhering to. It gives the inspiration to do better.”

Furthermore, an interviewee viewed RSMM as a “good starting point” for identifying considerations at various stages of the maturity of a research software project: “I think it is a good starting point to collect ideas what a software project should consider in its various stages...”. However, a challenge identified by one of the experts was that the users might face difficulty evaluating all the criteria independently due to the extensive number of practices in the model. This observation has led to plans to automate the assessment process using RSMM to make the evaluation more user-friendly.

Question 3 (Operational feasibility): Do you anticipate using RSMM (can be practically implemented) in your future work?

We received mixed answers to this question: ‘yes’ and ‘no’. One of the interviewees also suggested that RSMM should be tested by applying it to real-world projects or suggesting a case study.

“Potentially yes. The use case would be to use it to cross-check for an existing software project which aspects should probably be considered next. Not necessarily to rank a project by maturity level.”

Additionally, two of them responded “no” to this question. They indicated that there was no direct use of RSMM in their future work, and while the model might be valuable to others, it may not fit their specific needs or current working area.

Finally, when we asked for any feedback or comments on RSMM, one of the interviewees responded that security practices are context-specific and suggested separating security into sections and providing criteria for when it is necessary to focus on security. Interestingly, the same responses were received from many of the case study participants.

“...A suggestion would be to separate out the security requirement in a separate section and a criteria for determining if the security requirements are important. But otherwise, everything looks fine.”

Additionally, one of the responses was received for the model’s applicability that RSMM might not be fully applicable to all projects, mainly due to time, resources, or skills limitations. However, applying parts of the model can still bring improvements. In addition to this, one respondent also suggests visualizing RSMM to make it look better.

We observed some common themes in the responses from experts in both cases during the interview and after viewing RSMM v1.0. One significant observation is that some of the practices are context-specific. We wanted to test the applicability of the RSMM v1.0 with the case studies and then check the context-specific practices placement. The third evaluation phase was conducted during the case studies. The results are described in the following subsection.

3.2 Case studies responses

To validate RSMM, we conducted case studies involving participants from various research software projects to evaluate the model’s usefulness and applicability. This section presents the

questions and responses posed to the case study participants. Additionally, we have included the identified themes and corresponding sample responses in Table 6.

Table 6: Evaluation table: Results from case studies

Questions	Themes	Example excerpt(s)
Is the evaluation useful for your project?	Utility and Usefulness of the model	<i>“Yes, it was useful to have such a comprehensive and systematic overview of the different capabilities and focus areas.”</i>
	Feasibility and Prioritization of best practices	<i>“I think it is useful to review every now and then whether we ‘check all the boxes’ in terms of software best practices. However, I do think that some of these things cost quite some time, without much return in the long run...”</i>
	Reflection on current practices	<i>“I did learn what other people consider important when managing research code.”</i>
	Overlap and Redundancy in other frameworks	<i>“there is quite some redundancy among the various models and checklists. We have the OpenSSF badge, the FAIRSoftware badge, the eScience center guide, the Turning Way, and now your model, all with overlapping categories..”</i>
	Recommendations and Identifying gaps from the model	<i>“We learned that the biggest lack is in community support, bug/crash reporting and a clear communication of the overall vision and future software development plan for [software tool name].”</i>
Is RSMM complete?	Comprehensiveness and Completeness	<i>“It looks quite comprehensive to me.”, “We consider it very comprehensive and detailed. We do not see anything missing right now.”</i>
	Missing and Irrelevant practices	<i>“The only thing that struck me as odd was the idea with “chatbot support” on the project website.”, “For some software, security is less of a concern.”</i>
Do you intend to use RSMM to manage your project?	Model adoption and Practical use	<i>“I could use it as a reference”, “no intention right now, evaluation is not part of my job, I will use this model in future.”</i>
	Implementation challenges	<i>“Full compliance is hard with the resources we have, but we like to improve every year.”</i>

Question	Themes	Example excerpt(s)
	Stakeholder perception	<i>“I think it is a good check to have a look at every once in a while for each open source project. Not all points are relevant at every stage of the project but this can help you think about the next steps in the process.”</i>

Question 1: Is the evaluation useful for your project?

This question was asked to assess the practical relevance and applicability of RSMM from the end-user’s perspective. The responses are grouped into themes, and the identified themes are written below:

- **Usefulness of the model:** Many participants found that RSMM provides a comprehensive and systematic overview of capabilities and focus areas and offers a good framework for evaluation. Participants appreciated its usefulness, describing it as helpful and valuable to have this kind of mapping for practices and maturity levels.
- **Feasibility and Prioritization of best practices:** Participants acknowledged the value of periodically reviewing software best practices but highlighted the challenges of time and resource constraints. They noted that while some practices do not take much time to implement, others require significant effort with limited long-term benefits. It suggests that when choosing which best practices to adopt, it is important to weigh how much effort is needed against the value or impact they will provide. To support this, we recommend examining our dataset, which provides insights into when these practices have been implemented. Additionally, users can compare their practices with those of others and evaluate their project’s value or impact within the research context. This comparison helps users better understand the potential benefits of adopting specific practices.
- **Reflection on current practices:** Three respondents replied that they are already following many of the practices of RSMM in their daily work and identified areas for improvement. One response, *“I did learn what other people consider important when managing research code!”*, it highlights how participants gained valuable insights into what others consider essential practices. Some also learned about SBOM, which was new to them.
- **Overlap and Redundancy in other frameworks:** Participants noted significant redundancy among various models and checklists such as the OpenSSF badge, the FAIRSoftware badge, the eScience center guide and the Turning Way. Additionally, one participant stated, *“Several of these tools are in my opinion also not tailored enough towards research software.”*. This feedback reflects their concern that these frameworks are not customized to meet the unique needs of research software.
- **Recommendations and Identifying gaps from the model:** Participants identified specific, actionable steps for improvement, such as *Adopt a code of conduct*, *Document how to join the team*, *write a software management plan*, and *Document the running costs*. One participant noted, *“I’ve written down a few small improvements that I can reasonably make...”*. This comment describes how the model offers users recommendations for improvement.

Question 2: Is RSMM complete?

From this question, we seek feedback on whether the model covers all necessary aspects for managing research software projects, such as whether the model includes all the essential practices and applies to the diverse range of research software projects. Additionally, it is important to know whether RSMM provides enough detail and guidance for users to use it effectively. Extracted themes are provided below:

- **Comprehensiveness and Completeness:** Many respondents agreed that RSMM covers many best research software project management practices without noticeable omissions. One respondent stated, *“It looks very thorough and seems to cover many aspects,”* while another noted, *“It seems quite comprehensive”*.
- **Missing practices and Irrelevant practices:** One participant noted that a chat support system on the website does not apply to research software; similarly, security may be less of a concern for specific research software. Additionally, one participant suggested adding new practices to RSMM, such as explicitly managing the number of dependencies. While some participants feel that security-related practices may not be relevant for specific research software, there remains a bias towards including them in the model.

We received ten positive responses indicating that the model is comprehensive and complete, covering many practices. However, 3 participants provided negative feedback about RSMM and seven mixed opinions about RSMM. As a result, only 50% of the participants believe that RSMM is comprehensive and complete, with some expressing concerns about the feasibility of implementing all the practices. They noted that including too many aspects could lead to significant time investment with minimal return.

Question 3: Do you intend to use this model (RSMM) (practically implement) to manage your project?

We asked Question 3 to assess the practical applicability and adoption of the model.

- **Model adoption and Practical use:** From the responses, we understand that many respondents intended to use the model as a reference point or checklist. They value certain aspects or practices of the model.
- **Implementation challenges:** A few also reported worries about needing more resources, time, or personnel to implement the model entirely. These constraints prevent them from adopting the model in their work.
- **Stakeholder perception:** Several participants expressed a positive view of the model, acknowledging its broad scope and the importance of the practices it covers. However, only some of them also responded that they already use many practices of the model; thus, currently, they find the use of the model tiny in their work. Two of them also said they were interested in resolving issues rather than prioritizing the model’s maturity in the model. Some participants wanted to add educational materials to their model and were inspired to add a code of conduct, and others also shared their aim of improving sustainability. From this, it is clear that RSMM is helpful to researchers and RSEs who want to measure their project maturity. It is also beneficial to benchmark their projects with others, as one of the responses we received is that they are currently following or benchmarking their project with others to improve their software.

The respondents view RSMM as a helpful reference or checklist for managing research software projects. They see value in periodic assessments to guide research software project improvements. However, full compliance with the model is seen as challenging due to resource constraints. We received nine positive responses, six negative, and five mixed opinions.

In addition to the evaluation questions, we asked a few general questions to improve our RSMM with the other existing practices that they are following or guidelines they are following. The questions and responses are provided below:

Question 4: Did you follow other practices not included in the evaluation to improve your research software project management?

This question aims to gather insights on additional practices or strategies that case study participants have used in their projects apart from the RSMM practices. Several respondents highlighted the influence of external communities, meetups, or previous work experience on shaping their project management practices. Additionally, one of the participants added code refactoring for the code quality and other technical practices. Their insights are illustrated in the following quotes:

“We mostly followed the Astropy guidelines for affiliated packages. CI, docs, etc., are all part of a common framework.”

“I get inspiration from seeing how other research software projects manage themselves.”

“We also have documentation on the design and architecture of the software.”

These comments help us understand the alternative approaches and guidelines researchers currently use and gain a broader view of the practices used to improve research software project management. It also provides valuable feedback for enhancing RSMM by incorporating other helpful practices.

4 Case study projects

Our current study covers 18 case projects. This section provides a brief description of them.

Table 7: Case studies software and their description

Software	Software full name	Description
BridgeDb Java (Van Iersel et al., 2010)		a library that maps identifiers from one source to another. For example, it can map NCBI Gene identifiers to ensemble gene identifiers and DOIs to PubMed identifiers.
Kernel tuner (van Werkhoven, 2019)		simplifies the development of highly optimised and auto-tuned CUDA, OpenCL, and C code, supporting many advanced use-cases and optimisation strategies that speed up the auto-tuning process.

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Software	Software full name	Description
DIANNA (Ranguelova et al., 2019)	Deep Insight And Neural Network Analysis	a Python package that brings explainable AI (XAI) to the research project. It wraps carefully selected XAI methods in a simple, uniform interface.
DALES (Arabas et al., 2024)	Dutch Atmospheric Large Eddy Simulation	a large-eddy simulation code designed for studies of the physics of the atmospheric boundary layer, including convective and stable boundary layers as well as cloudy boundary layers.
3D Slicer (Fedorov et al., 2012)		a free, open-source software for visualisation, processing, segmentation, registration, and analysis of medical, biomedical, and other 3D images and meshes; and planning and navigating image-guided procedures.
OceanParcels (Van Sebille et al., 2024)	Ocean Probably A Really Computationally Efficient Lagrangian Simulator	project develops Parcels, a set of Python classes and methods to create customisable particle tracking simulations using output from Ocean Circulation models. Parcels can track passive and active particulates such as water, plankton, plastic and fish.
Haddock3 (Teixeira et al., 2024)	High Ambiguity Driven protein-protein DOCKing	a modular software for the integrative modelling and refinement of biomolecular complexes.
LitStudy (Heldens et al., 2022)		explores scientific literature using Python from the comfort of a Jupyter notebook.
Scholia (Nielsen et al., 2017)		a Graphical User Interface around Wikidata that uses SPARQL to collect data.
eWaterCycle (Verhoeven et al., 2024)		package makes it easier to use hydrological models without having intimate knowledge about how to install and run the models.
ASTRA Toolbox (van Aarle et al., 2016)		a Python and MATLAB library of flexible, high-performance GPU-accelerated primitives for 2D and 3D tomography.
Pyglotaran (Weißenborn et al., 2024)	A Python library for Global and Target Analysis of time-resolved spectroscopy data	a framework for the analysis of time-resolved spectroscopy measurements in the study of energy transfer pathways in photosynthesis, or the characterization of energy transfer (in-)efficiencies in photovoltaics.
MAGMA celltyping (de Leeuw et al., 2015)	Multi-marker Analysis of GenoMic Annotation celltyping	an R package containing code used to test which cell types can explain the heritability signal from GWAS summary statistics.

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Software	Software full name	Description
MSS (Bauer et al., 2025)	Mission Support System	software written by scientists in atmospheric science. The purpose is to have a tool that simplifies the process of planning a scientific flight in which parameters of the atmosphere are measured. The research aircraft typically carry a comprehensive scientific payload comprising data acquisition instruments from different companies and research institutions.
oemof.solph (Krien et al., 2024)		a model generator for energy system modelling and optimisation (LP/MILP).
MUSCLE3 (Veen and Sebregts, 2024)	the third incarnation of the Multiscale Coupling Library and Environment	Using MUSCLE3 it is possible to connect multiple simulation models together into a multiscale simulation.
PopPUNK (Lees et al., 2019)	POPulation Partitioning Using Nucleotide Kmers	a powerful tool designed for clustering genomes, here the clusters are the variable-length k-mer clusters (VLKCs). Biologically, these clusters often correspond to distinct strains of a species. The tool categorises subclusters of strains as lineages, providing a detailed classification within the broader clusters.
Eclipse SUMO (Alvarez Lopez et al., 2018)	Eclipse Simulation of Urban MObility	an open-source, highly portable, microscopic and continuous traffic simulation package that handles large networks. It allows for intermodal simulation, including pedestrians, and comes with a large set of tools for scenario creation.

5 Assessment

Table 8 includes 79 practices, self assessment questions and evidence, where the project owners look into for the practices.

The proposed Algorithm 1 describes a step-by-step process for conducting a maturity assessment of research software projects. Initially, the assessment begins by selecting a research software project whose maturity in research software project management is to be evaluated. Use RSMM v1.0, and transform each practice defined in the model into a self-assessment question (Table 8) to determine whether the practice is implemented in the selected project.

For each practice, the assessor records “Yes” if the practice is implemented and “No” if it is not implemented. After completing the evaluation for a focus area, the maturity level is determined as the highest level in the longest continuous sequence for which all practices are marked “Yes.” For example, if the maturity levels of the first, second, and third capabilities are 3, 2, and 2, respectively, the maturity level of the focus area is 2. This process is repeated for each focus area to be measured, while any focus areas that are not relevant to the assessment may be excluded.

During the case studies, participants received only descriptions of the practices rather than explicit assessment questions. As a result, participants added clarification questions in the shared Excel sheet. Therefore, we added a separate section describing the assessment procedure in this paper to clarify the evaluation process. Figure 4 presents an example of the Excel data set that we provided to the owner of the case study project to review and validate the case study results. We requested that project owners verify our initial assessments: cells highlighted in green indicate practices they confirmed as being followed, whereas cells highlighted in red indicate practices that were not followed. Project owners were asked to validate these classifications, and they added comments when they disagreed with our findings. Based on their feedback, we subsequently revised the responses. They also provided additional details regarding the practices they are following. To assess maturity according to Algorithm 1, users can record “Yes” or “No” responses in the ‘practice’ cells.

Table 8: Assessment table

Practice name	Questions	Evidence
File issues in an issue tracker	Are bugs, feature requests, and tasks recorded in an issue tracking system?	Issue tracker entries (e.g., GitHub Issues, GitLab Issues), issue logs
Act on feedback	Does the project systematically collect and project owners act on user feedback?	Issue tracker discussions, surveys, change logs
Manage requirements explicitly	Are project requirements documented and tracked?	Requirements documents, labeled issues, roadmap
Perform release management	Are releases planned, versioned, and documented?	Release notes, version tags, schedules
Communicate roadmap	Is a public roadmap available to stakeholders?	Roadmap page, project boards
Provide a coding standard	Is a coding standard documented and communicated to contributors?	CONTRIBUTING.md, style guide
Conduct code reviews	Are code changes peer-reviewed before merging?	Pull request reviews
Implement continuous integration (CI)	Are automated builds and tests triggered on each code change?	CI configuration files, build logs
Provide executable tests	Are automated tests provided and maintained?	Test directories, CI reports
Use crash reporting	Are runtime failures systematically monitored and reported?	Crash logs, monitoring tools
Conduct security reviews	Are security vulnerabilities periodically reviewed?	Security reports, issue tracker entries
Measure project stability continuously	Are stability metrics tracked over time?	Dashboards, defect reports

Practice name	Questions	Evidence
Define code coverage targets	Are test coverage targets defined and monitored?	Coverage reports, badges
Execute tests in a public workflow	Are tests executed in publicly visible CI pipelines?	Public CI pipelines, badges
Follow an industry standard for security	Does the project follow recognized security standards?	Documentation referencing standards
Store project in public repository with version control	Is the project stored in a public version-controlled repository?	Repository URL
Use public communication platform	Does the project use public platforms for communication?	Mailing lists, forums, chats
Provide news letter	Does the project publish periodic newsletters or updates?	Newsletter archives
Provide community website	Does the project maintain a community website?	Website URL, community discussions
Define a clear audience for the project	Is the target audience explicitly defined?	Project documentation, website description
Perform infrequent impact measurement	Is project impact measured occasionally?	Usage reports, citations, download statistics
Evaluate whether the audience's goals are met	Is user satisfaction or goal attainment evaluated?	Surveys, feedback reports
Perform continuous impact measurement	Are impact metrics monitored continuously?	Dashboards, analytics reports
Explore new audiences regularly	Does the project actively seek new user communities?	Outreach plans, workshop materials
Acquire temporary funding	Has the project obtained short-term or grant-based funding?	Grant proposals, funding acknowledgements
Write software management plan	Is a software management plan documented?	Software management plan document
Obtain support from a national research software center	Is the project supported by a national RSE or software center?	Support agreements, acknowledgements
Acquire viable pathways for project sustainability	Are long-term sustainability strategies documented?	Sustainability plans, governance documents
Secure continuous funding	Is recurring or long-term funding secured?	Multi-year grants, institutional funding letters
Define end-of-life policy	Is a policy defined for project retirement or archival?	End-of-life policy document
Make code citable	Is the software assigned a persistent identifier (e.g., DOI)?	Zenodo DOI, citation file (CITATION.cff)
Enable indexing of project meta-data	Is project metadata indexed in registries?	Registry entries, metadata files

Practice name	Questions	Evidence
Promote the project continuously	Is the project actively promoted?	Blog posts, social media, conference presentations
Publish in a research software directory	Is the project listed in a research software registry?	Registry URL (e.g., RSD, bio.tools)
Acquire research software center acknowledgement	Is the project acknowledged by an RSE center?	Acknowledgement statements
Enable indexing of the project's source code	Is the source code indexed by search services?	GitHub, Software Heritage entries
Garner industrial partner adoption	Is the software adopted by industry partners?	Case studies, partner testimonials
Analyze privacy usage impact	Are privacy implications assessed?	Privacy impact assessment documents
Analyze ethical consequences of project use	Are ethical implications evaluated?	Ethics statements, risk assessments
Document the cost of running the application	Are operational costs documented?	Cost reports, budgeting documents
Consider total energy consumption	Is energy consumption evaluated?	Energy usage reports, green computing statements
Acknowledge partners and funding agencies on website	Are partners and funders acknowledged publicly?	Website acknowledgements section
Develop advanced partnership model	Is a formal partnership or governance model defined?	Governance charters
Impose community norms	Are community norms defined and enforced?	Community guidelines document
Onboard researchers as part of the community	Is there an onboarding process for new contributors?	Onboarding documentation
Develop code of conduct	Is a code of conduct published?	CODE OF CONDUCT.md
Appoint support team	Is a dedicated support team identified?	Team page, support contacts
Organize community events	Are community events organized?	Workshop announcements, event reports
Provide front page chat support	Is real-time chat support available on the project homepage?	Chat widget
Focus on diversity and inclusion	Are diversity and inclusion (D&I) policies implemented?	D&I policy statements
Make developer names and roles publicly available	Are developer roles and responsibilities documented?	CONTRIBUTING.md, Team page, governance docs
Document how to join the team	Are instructions provided for joining the team?	CONTRIBUTING.md, onboarding guide
Set maximum response time for pull requests	Is a response time policy defined for contributions?	Contribution policy documents

Practice name	Questions	Evidence
Provide access to developer training and skill development	Are training resources provided to developers?	Training materials, workshop announcements
Select a license	Is an open-source license selected?	LICENSE file
Get institutional support for license choice	Is the license choice approved by the institution?	Institutional policy documents
Evaluate license policy regularly	Is the licensing policy periodically reviewed?	Governance meeting notes
Provide a statement of purpose	Is the project purpose clearly stated?	README, website mission statement
Provide a simple how to use	Is basic usage documentation provided?	Quick-start guide
Provide online tutorials	Are online tutorials available?	Tutorial web pages, videos
Provide a read me file with project explanation	Is a README explaining the project provided?	README.md
Provide a how-to guide	Are detailed how-to guides available?	Documentation guides
Provide a common example usage	Are example use cases provided?	Example scripts, notebooks
Provide documentation as repository/documentation wiki	Is documentation hosted in a wiki or docs repository?	Wiki or docs site
Provide API documentation	Is API documentation available?	API docs site, autogenerated docs
Use common non-exotic or established technology	Does the project use widely adopted technologies?	Technology stack documentation
Facilitate integration into scientific workflow	Can the software integrate into research workflows?	Workflow examples, pipeline templates
Evaluate technology relevance regularly	Is the technology stack periodically reviewed?	Technical review reports
Provide instructions on how to put into research workflow	Are workflow integration instructions provided?	Documentation guides
Provide instructions on how to make part of a replication package	Are replication package instructions provided?	Replication documentation
Make part of standardized workflows	Is the software included in standard workflow frameworks?	Workflow templates
Make part of a replication package	Is the software included in replication packages?	Replication package repositories
Develop generic educational materials	Are teaching materials developed?	Slides, textbooks, tutorials
Organize training events in person	Are in-person training events organized?	Workshop announcements

Practice name	Questions	Evidence
Make project part of an educational program	Is the project integrated into formal education?	Course syllabi
Provide standard deployment tools	Are deployment tools provided (e.g., Docker, installers)?	Dockerfiles, installation scripts
Enable deployment on a wide range of technology	Can the software run on multiple platforms?	Platform support documentation
Provide coordination mechanisms for workflow distribution over different machines	Are distributed workflow mechanisms supported?	Workflow orchestration documentation
Generate SBOM	Is a Software Bill of Materials generated?	SBOM files (e.g., SPDX, CycloneDX)

Algorithm 1 Maturity Measurement for Any Research Software Project

Input: Software project

Output: Maturity level of the project

1. *Select any Project:* Choose the software project for which you want to measure maturity.
 2. *Start Maturity Model Assessment:* Initiate the assessment of the project using RSMM v1.0.
 3. *Evaluate Practices:* Examine whether the selected project follows the practices outlined in the first focus area of a Maturity Model. If a practice is followed, mark ‘yes’; otherwise, mark ‘no’. Consider only the cell with practices.
 4. *Check Maturity Levels:* Inspect the maturity columns for the focus area. If a level contains no practices, skip it; all practices at lower levels must be marked “Yes” to attain a higher level. Determine the maturity level as the highest level in the longest continuous sequence for which all practices are marked “Yes.”
 5. *Return:* Maturity level of the project for the particular focus area.
 6. *Repeat:* Repeat Steps 3, 4 and 5 for all other focus areas.
 7. *Skip:* Skip any focus area that you do not want to include in the evaluation.
 8. **Return:** Maturity level of the project.
-

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Focus Area	Capability	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Software Project Management	Requirements		File issues in an issue tracker	Act on feedback [1]				Manage requirements explicitly [2]	Perform release management		Communicate roadmap [3]
	Code quality and security	Provide a coding standard	Conduct code reviews	Implement continuous integration	Provide executable tests [4]	Use crash reporting	Conduct security reviews	Measure project stability	Define code coverage targets	Execute tests in a public workflow [5]	Follow an industry standard for security (e.g., OWASP SAMM, BSIMM, OpenSSF, etc.)
	Communication and Collaboration			Store project in public repository with version control				Use public communication platform (e.g., email list, Slack, etc.)	Provide news letter		Provide community website
Research Software Management		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	Impact measurement		Define a clear audience for the project	Perform infrequent impact measurement [6]				Evaluate whether the audience's goals are met		Perform continuous impact measurement	Explore new audiences regularly
	Sustainability		Acquire temporary funding		Write software management plan			Obtain support from a national research software center	Acquire viable pathways for project sustainability	Secure continuous funding	Define end-of-life policy
	Visibility	Make code citable		Enable indexing of project meta-data	Promote the project continuously	Publish in a research software directory	Acquire research software center acknowledgment [7]	Enable indexing of the project's source code [8]			Garner industrial partner adoption
	Usage costs & Ethics				Analyze privacy usage impact	Analyze ethical consequences of project use	Document the cost of running the application	Consider total energy consumption			
Community Engagement		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	Partnerships				Acknowledge partners and funding agencies on website			Develop advanced partnership model [9]			
	Community			Impose community norms	Onboard researchers as part of the community [10]	Develop code of conduct	Appoint support team [11]	Organize community events		Provide front page chat support	Focus on diversity and inclusion
	Developers		Make developer names and roles publicly available				Document how to join the team		Set maximum response time for pull requests	Provide access to developer training and skill development [12]	
	Licensing	Select a license		Get institutional support for license choice					Evaluate license policy regularly [13]		
Software Adoptability		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	Ease of use		Provide a statement of purpose [14]	Provide a simple how to use [15]			Provide online tutorials				
	Documentation		Provide a readme file with project explanation	Provide a how-to guide	Provide a common example usage		Provide a documentation as repository/documentation/wiki [16]		Provide API documentation		
	Technology		Use common non-exotic or established technology		Facilitate integration into scientific workflow					Evaluate technology relevance regularly	
	Reproducibility		Provide instructions on how to put into research workflow		Provide instructions on how to make part of a replication package	Make part of standardized workflows		Make part of a replication package			
	Education					Develop generic educational materials				Organize training events in person	Make project part of an educational program [17]
	Deployability						Provide with standard deployment tools (Enable deployment on a wide range of technology	Provide coordination mechanisms for workflow distribution over different machines	Generate SBOM [18]	

Figure 4: An overview of how a research software project scores on the RSMM, developed by the eScience Center, Leiden University, and Utrecht University. Green practices are observably implemented (assessment performed by a PhD student) and red practices have not observably been implemented.